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Immunoglobulin gene segment activation is a feature of disease progression and lymph node metastasis in humans with solid tumors.

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We describe here recurrent immunoglobulin rearrangement events that occur as a function or product of metastasis to the lymph nodes in patients with a solid tumor (cancer) in either the breast or colon/rectum. Immunoglobulin rearrangement events could be presumed to occur as a general function of disease progression in humans with cancer separate from metastasis to the lymph nodes.

Results

GSE174519

n=4 primary tumor (human CRC)
n=3 lymph node metastasis (human CRC)

We studied the total transcriptome of (measured total transcription in the tumors of) humans with colorectal cancer: the primary tumor and the lymph node metastasis. Changes in immunoglobulin gene segment expression were among the most significant (quantitatively largest) gene expression changes across tumor evolution (when comparing total transcription in the primary tumor and lymph node metastasis). In this case, Ig transcriptional activity appeared to be silenced as the disease progressed to the lymph nodes; this appears to be an artifact of small sample size (see Example #3).

I. Changes in transcriptional activity from immunoglobulin gene segments associated with metastasis to the lymph nodes occur in multiple solid tumor types - they are not specific to breast cancer.

GSE12225

We compared total transcription based on nodal involvement in primary tumors from humans with stage T2N0 or T2N1 colorectal cancer: these tumors are equivalent in size but different as to whether the disease has spread to the lymph nodes (N0 vs N1).

n=17 T2N0
n=6 T2N1

GSE190609

II. Transcriptional activity from immunoglobulin gene segments - and changes in this activity across disease progression - are likely a common feature in solid tumor biology, and activation of expression is conserved between different cancer types (e.g., in the colon and in the breast)

n=35 primary tumor (CRC; human)
n=11 lymph node metastasis (CRC)

28791	1.04e-11	0.6465	-6.801195	-4.397049	119.78	IGLV3-27	Rank: 47/20020
28451	8.13e-07	0.5083	-4.9322057	-2.5069592	39.51	IGHV3-9	Rank: 401/20020
28825	1.38e-05	0.4003	-4.3465424	-1.7398785	609.68	IGLV1-40	Rank: 640/20020
28907	1.64e-05	0.5835	-4.3087341	-2.5143222	15.67	IGKV5-2	Rank: 660/20020
28939	2.98e-05	0.5423	-4.1749637	-2.2642298	112.21	IGKV1-13	Rank: 738/20020

III. Immunoglobulin gene rearrangement is a central feature of metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer.

GSE44408

IGHM activation in lymph node metastasis.

probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
212827_at	8.37E-08	-6.7687005	7.78727	-2.58249403	IGHM	11/22277	99.95
=209374_s_at	1.22E-02	-2.6445802	-3.02125	-1.25180586	IGHM	690/22277	96.9

IGHV5-78 activation in lymph node metastasis.

probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
210450_at	4.48E-06	-5.4394615	4.1583	-0.22501985	IGHV5-78	48/22277	99.8

IGH activation in lymph node metastasis.

probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
215118_s_at	9.23E-05	-4.4265388	1.38526	-1.32574227	IGH	110/22277	99.5

IGHD activation in lymph node metastasis.

probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
222285_at	1.20E-02	-2.652723	-3.00384	-0.21393274	IGHD	683/22277	96.9

We next studied a separate transcriptome set representing primary tumors from patients who did or did not possess metastases to the lymph nodes.

When comparing the primary tumors of breast cancer patients who do or do not have lymph node metastasis, immunoglobulin gene rearrangement was

- Already observable (apparent) in the primary tumor,
- Much higher in patients who do have lymph node metastasis and,
- among the largest differences transcriptome-wide when comparing the primary tumors of breast cancer patients with or without lymph node metastasis.

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Discussion

We describe here recurrent immunoglobulin rearrangement events that occur as a function or product of metastasis to the lymph nodes in patients with a solid tumor (cancer) in either the breast or colon/rectum. Immunoglobulin rearrangement events could be presumed to occur as a general function of disease progression in humans with cancer separate from metastasis to the lymph nodes.

1 **Supplemental Data**

2
3 S1: Supplemental Data for:

4 "When comparing the primary tumors of breast cancer patients who do or do not have lymph node
5 metastasis, immunoglobulin gene rearrangement was

- 6 a. Already observable (apparent) in the primary tumor,
7 b. Much higher in patients who do have lymph node metastasis and,
8 c. among the largest differences transcriptome-wide when comparing the primary tumors of breast
9 cancer patients with or without lymph node metastasis"

10 GSE163346

11 Rank: 478/23176

12 ID: 28778

13 p-value: 2.12E-03

14 lfcse: 1.329

15 Stat: -3.0728858

16 log2FC: -4.0835758

17 Basemean: 247.08

18 Gene: IGLV 6-57

19 Rank: 520/23176

20 ID: 28388

21 p-value: 2.55E-03

22 lfcse: 1.385

23 Stat: -3.0175136

24 log2FC: -4.1799283

25 Basemean: 667.32

26 Gene: IGHV5-51

27 Rank: 601/23176

28 ID: 3505

P-value: 3.45E-03

lfcse: 1.354

Stat: -2.9247188

log2FC: -3.9598561

Basemean: 1052.46

Gene: IGHGP

Rank: 673/23176

ID: 28398

P-value: 4.40E-03

lfcse: 1.444

Stat: -2.8478303

log2FC: -4.11282

Basemean: 95.59

Gene: IGHV4-30-2

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Methods

We used a systems biologic approach to understanding common transcriptional events occurring in human cancer. We measured total transcription and differential expression using microarray and RNA-sequencing and R-based computational methods.